

PARAMETERS AFFECT THE CRYSTALLIZATION OF CARBON FIBER
REINFORCED POLYETHER ETHER KETONE COMPOSITES (I)

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ABSTRACT

A study has been conducted to investigate the parameters affect the crystallization of carbon fiber (C.F.) reinforced Polyether Ether Ketone (PEEK). Effects of the fiber content , processing conditions on the crystallization behavior of PEEK/C.F. were studied under isothermal and non-isothermal crystallization conditions.

From the DSC thermograms, it was found that the regularity and fusion temperature of composite were affected by the fiber reinforcement. By utilizing the Avrami equation, kinetic constant of nucleation-constant, n , was obtained for different processing conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) is one of high performance thermoplastic resins. It shows excellent properties including high tensile strength , high melting point , super interlaminar fracture toughness , etc. Since it is a semi-crystalline resin , the crystallization behavior affects the mechanical properties, chemical resistance , dimensional stability and interface between fiber and matrix. Several researches (1-4) on crystallization of neat PEEK resin have been conducted ; however , the effect of fiber on the crystallization of PEEK composites is ambiguous. This research investigates the effect of carbon fiber cloth on the crystallization behavior of PEEK/C.F. composites under isothermal-crystallization and non-isothermal crystallization processing conditions by DSC.

Crystallization mechanism includes nucleation and spherulite growth (1). From thermodynamics concept, it is clear that when polymer is crystallized its molecules were arranged in order , entropy will be decreased and shows exothermic behavior. The kinetics of crystallization and thermal properties can be examined by DSC(2-5).

At isothermal-crystallization , the time-dependent crystallization can be explained by means of Avrami equation (6) :

$$(X_t - X_\infty) / X_\infty = \text{EXP}(-Kt)^n \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

where X_t and X_∞ are the weight fraction of crystallized materials at time t and ∞ ; k is the rate constant and n is a nonstant. Hence,

$$\log\{-\ln(1-X_t/X_\infty)\} = n \log t + \log k \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

From the slope and intercept of the plots of $\log\{-\ln(1-X_t/X_\infty)\}$ versus $\log t$, n and k can be obtained. The rate of heat of crystallization, (dH_t/dt) , can be measured by DSC. By integrating these curves one can determine the the relative extent of crystallization(3) i.e.:

$$X_t/X_\infty = \int_0^t (dH_t/dt) dt / \int_0^\infty (dH_t/dt) dt \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Composite laminate

A semi-crystalline PEEK sheet with 5 mil thickness was supplied by I.C.I. Co. U.K., and the reinforced carbon fiber woven cloth (#3101, 200g/m) was obtained by Toho Co. Japan. Using film stacking process, PEEK film and carbon fiber were laminated at 390°C with various fiber contents(e.g. 25 % wt., 41 % wt., 60 % wt.).

2. Isothermal crystallization

a. Specimens were heated to 400°C, and held for 10 min. to make sure all the nuclei are destroyed. Then samples were cooled to T_c rapidly at the cooling rate, 320°C/min the change of energy was recorded by DSC.

b. Specimens were heated to 400°C, and held for 10 min., then were quenched by liquid nitrogen to obtain amorphous type composites. Those amorphous specimen were heated to T_c at heating rate 80°C/min and were scanned by DSC.

3. Non-isothermal crystallization

Specimens (PEEK/C.F.) were heated to 400°C and held for 10 min., then were cooled at various rates: 40°C/min, 20°C/min, 10°C/min and 5°C/min, using a Perkin Elemer DSC-2.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. Isothermal-crystallization of PEEK/C.F. composites

a. Melting behavior

Figures 1 to 4 show DSC heating scans of a series of

samples containing various fiber contents which had been crystallized isothermally at different temperatures. These thermograms curves were characterized by two melting processes. These results similar to the behavior of neat PEEK resin and can be explained in terms of the recrystallization phenomenon described by G. M. Tung and P.J. Dynes.(7) The effect of carbon fiber on the melting point is less sensitive ; however, it is obvious that carbon fiber destroys the structure of spherulite and lowers the melting temperatures of composites slightly as can be seen from Figures 5 and 6 .

b. Crystallization kinetics -Avrami equation

According to equation 1 , the plots of $\log\{-\ln(1-X_t/X_\infty)\}$ versus $\log t$ for PEEK/C.F. containing various fiber contents at $T_c=280^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_c=180^\circ\text{C}$ are shown in Figures 7 and 8 , respectively. The values of n and k were determined from the slope and intercept of curve. The crystallization kinetics of PEEK/C.F. follow a dual mechanism. Slope of the first portion , $n=2.7$, while the second portion , $n=1.0$ at $T_c=280^\circ\text{C}$. At $T_c=180^\circ\text{C}$, $n=1.3$ for first section and $n=1.0$ for second section. The value , $n=2.7$, might refer to a spherulitic , diffusion-controlled and three dimensional growth of crystallization , and $n=1.0$ might refer to a rod-shaped, diffusion-controlled , one dimensional growth of crystallization. Comparing Figure 7 with Figure 8 , the growth mechanism of spherulite in the isothermal crystallization process from molten state and from solid amorphous state are different. The effect of carbon fiber on the morphology of PEEK/C.F. composites is insignificant ; however , the crystallization rate and crystallization rate constant are decreased (as shown in Table 1) .The higher the carbon fiber content , the slower the crystallization rate. The crystallization rate of composites reaches a maximum in the temperature range between 220°C and 230°C . (as shown in Figure 9)

2. Non-isothermal crystallization

Figures 10 to 11 are the DSC thermograms at various cooling rates. The higher the carbon fiber content , the lower the crystallization temperature (T_c). These phenomena indicate that carbon fiber might increase the crystallization rate and PEEK might be easier to crystallize. The higher the carbon fiber content, the lower the supercooling degree, hence the composite is easier to crystallize. It was confirmed that carbon fiber may induce transcristalline (8) at certain condition which may be the reason for the increasing of crystallization rate. Figures 12 and 13 illustrate the effect of cooling rate on the DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composites , one can see the higher the cooling rate , the narrower the exotherm curve. Figures 14 and 15 show DSC heating scans of a series

of samples which were crystallized non-isothermally at various cooling rates. Carbon fiber inhibits the growth of spherulite, destroys the regularity of spherulite and lowers the melting temperature of PEEK/C.F. composites.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of carbon fiber cloth on the crystallization behavior of PEEK/C.F. composites can be concluded as in following :

1. Both in the isothermal and non-isothermal crystallization process, the carbon fiber reinforcement destroys the regularity of spherulite and reduces the fusion temperature of PEEK/C.F. composites.
2. Carbon fiber reduces the crystallization rate. The higher the carbon fiber content, the slower the crystallization rate of PEEK/C.F. composites in the isothermal crystallization process.
3. Comparing the morphology, mechanisms of spherulite growth in the isothermal crystallization process from melt state with those from solid amorphous state, they are quite different. (e.g. $n = 2.7$ for the former, $n = 1.0$ for the latter)
4. In the non-isothermal crystallization process, carbon fiber may induce transcrystalline which will increase the crystallization rate. The higher the carbon fiber content, the faster the crystallization rate.

REFERENCES

1. D. J. Blundell, SAMPE Quarterly, October, 1 (1985).
2. J. P. Jog, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 30, 997 (1985).
3. J. N. Hay, P. A. Fitzgerald and M. Wilos, Polymer, 17, 1015 (1976).
4. Chris N. Velisaris and James C. Seferis, Polym. Eng. and Sci., 26(22), 1574 (1986).
5. D. G. Brady, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 20, 2541 (1976).
6. M. Avrami, J. Chem. Phys., 7, 1103 (1939) & 8, 212 (1940)
7. G. M. Tung and P. J. Dynes, J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 33, 505 (1987)
8. J. T. Hartness, SAMPE Journal, Sep./Oct., 13 (1984).

9. D. J. Blundell and B. N. Osborn , Polymer , 24, 953 (1983).

Table 1. Rate Constant, K , obtained from Avrami Equation at $T_c = 280^\circ\text{C}$ and 180°C for PEEK/C.F.Composites with various carbon fiber contents.

C.F.Content % Wt.	0	25	41	60
K at $T_c = 280^\circ\text{C}$	0.0210	0.0174	0.0145	0.0110
K at $T_c = 180^\circ\text{C}$	0.1620	0.1510	0.1020	0.0721

Fig. 1. DSC thermograms of PEEK neat resin crystallized at various temperatures.

Fig. 3. DSC thermograms of PEEK neat resin crystallized at various temperatures.

Fig. 2. DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composite crystallized at various temperatures. (fiber content 60%wt)

Fig. 4. DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composite crystallized at various temperatures. (fiber content 60%wt)

Fig. 5. Effect of carbon fiber content on the DSC thermograms of PEEK composites at $T_c=290^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 6. Effect of carbon fiber content on the DSC thermograms of PEEK composites at $T_c=270^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 7. Plot of $\log(-\ln(1-x(t)/X_m))$ vs. $\log t$ of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composites with various fiber content at $T_c=280^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 8. Plot of $\log(-\ln(1-x(t)/X_m))$ vs. $\log t$ of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composites with various fiber content at $T_c=180^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 9. Dependence of t_{\max} on crystallization temperature of carbon fiber reinforced PEEK composites with various contents.

Fig. 10. Effect of carbon fiber content on the DSC thermograms of PEEK composites at $40^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ cooling rate.

Fig. 11. Effect of carbon fiber content on the DSC thermograms of PEEK composites at 5°C/min. cooling rate.

Fig. 12. Effect of cooling rate on the DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composite. (fiber content 0%)

Fig. 14. Effect of carbon fiber content on the melting behavior of PEEK/C.F. composites at 40°C/min. cooling rate.

Fig. 13. Effect of cooling rate on the DSC thermograms of PEEK/C.F. composite. (fiber content 25%wt)

Fig. 15. Effect of carbon fiber content on the melting behavior of PEEK/C.F. composites at 5°C/min. cooling rate.